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Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026) is conducting transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. By engaging diverse stakeholders and exploring plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries the project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 5 concerns landscape scale engagement and research and WP6 supports inter-landscape, global and EU dialogues on transformative change pathways. Here we present a synthesis of a dialogue held on 19 March 2025 with mainly Dutch based academic, NGO, CSO, finance and government stakeholders' on landscape approaches. Understanding the impacts and potential of landscape approaches means understanding and identifying factors in human society at both the individual and collective levels, including behavioural, social, cultural, economic, institutional, technical and technological dimensions, that may be leveraged to bring about transformative change at landscape scale, for different and multiple social, economic and environmental goals in the context of sustainable development. The main conclusions of the dialogue with academic, implementing and financing stakeholders of landscape approaches about their impacts and potential to bring about transformative change at landscape scale are whilst robust evidence is generally lacking on their impacts, landscape approaches when implemented taking account of current and historical setting, could support transformative change. Issues of dichotomies, systems thinking, stakeholder engagement, power, learning, monitoring and evaluation, and long time scales are seen as key determinants of how transformative or incremental change can be leveraged,

This report will be followed by reports on other dialogues on different scales which contribute to consumer and producer landscape perspectives on transformative change of food systems towards biodiversity and equity.

Glossary

See [TC4BE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions.

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TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project2, (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.

Background

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales.

There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant. The TCforBE project supports **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems**. It engages diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher-led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 involves conceptual framing, synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape, and global and EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrifood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrifood systems,

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrifood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity and equity.

- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agrifood system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.
- Global dialogues, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, linking the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by dissemination and communication activities.

D6.2 Landscape Approaches Dialogue

Table 1 TC4BE Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics
Cameroon	Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emerging cocoa agrofood systems export timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP) trade, mining Medium-high levels of telecoupling Sustainability landscape initiatives (SLI) e.g. Dja Green cocoa landscape Large areas of rapidly degrading high-biodiversity forests, increasing agriculture
Colombia	Eastern Plains Llanos Orientales Magdalena River Cauca River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, and reforestation programs. Megadiverse landscapes 20% in conservation and 30% in communal lands but facing violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence. Appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders
Kenya	Mau forest – Masai - Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wetlands - expanding rice production and fish farming, and grasslands with grazing systems High biodiversity forests, conservation areas Tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP-horticulture systems Medium levels of telecoupling Large areas of high biodiversity forest ecosystems & extensive agriculture Regenerative change & SLIs: MaMaSe program
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grasslands (grazing systems) and tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems High biodiversity forests, conservation areas Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture Medium-high levels of telecoupling SLIs: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration

I. Introduction

1.1 Problem context

Landscape approaches are seen as potential but complex strategies to achieve systemic change in the nexus of climate, biodiversity, food, water, energy and livelihoods. This transdisciplinary, integrated space-place based approach requires context specific strategies at multiple levels. International NGO's, mainly from conservation and development perspectives have increasingly initiated landscape approaches¹ across the globe, in partnerships with governments, communities, knowledge organisations, private sector and other stakeholders in the last two decades. These experiences have led to different understandings of how landscape approaches should and could be implemented, definitions and perceptions of impacts of a landscape approach. The definitions used in this dialogue are provided by ISEAL Alliance in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Definitions of landscape, landscape approach and landscape initiative

Definitions

Landscape

Socio-ecological system, defined by a geographic area with common and interacting ecological and socioeconomic characteristics. A landscape may be delineated based on river basins, seascapes, ecosystems, jurisdictions, productive boundaries, or in other ways.

Landscape Approach

A management approach focused on multi-stakeholder collaboration to advance shared sustainability goals and build resilience at landscape scale.

Landscape Initiative

The multi-stakeholder initiative that operationalizes a landscape approach in a particular landscape, by setting common goals, taking collective action while reconciling different interests, and monitoring progress towards shared sustainability goals and outcomes at a landscape scale.

Transformative change refers to *fundamental, system-wide reorganisation across technological, economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values, recognising the depth, breadth and dynamics of system reorganisation. Depth refers to change that goes beyond addressing the symptoms of environmental change or their proximate drivers, such as new technologies, incentive systems or protected areas, to include changes to underlying drivers, including consumption preferences, beliefs, ideologies and social inequalities*². Understanding the impacts and potential of landscape approaches means understanding and identifying factors in human society at both the individual and collective levels, including behavioural, social, cultural, economic, institutional, technical and technological dimensions, that may be leveraged to bring about transformative change at landscape scale, for different and multiple social, economic and environmental goals in the context of sustainable development.

1.2 Aims

In partnership with the CIFOR-ICRAF [Global Landscapes Forum \(GLF\)](#), we are holding global dialogues on transformative change pathways for agrofood systems. The dialogues at different scales engage diverse agro-food system stakeholders to explore transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity, with attention to climate-biodiversity-economics-equity trade-offs, spillages and synergies, thereby enhancing the understanding and capacity (care-knowledge-agency) of participants.

This **Landscape Approach dialogue** aims to inform on-going practices of participants, and feed into these dialogues, providing evidence of how landscape approaches do and can fit into transformative change, as framed by IPBES and the upcoming [Scoping report for a second global assessment of biodiversity and ecosystem services](#).

¹ The term landscape approach is used here, also termed 'integrated landscape approach', 'territorial' or 'jurisdictional approach'. See the glossary, Arts et al., (2017) and [ISEAL Alliance](#) for definitions.

² [Transformative change | IPBES secretariat](#)

2. Methodology

We organised a one-day dialogue on Wednesday 19 March 2025 from 09.00 to 16.30 at the NcountR room, Impulse Building, Wageningen UR Campus, Wageningen, The Netherlands. This brought together grounded experience from practitioners together with academic evidence from researchers on the transformative potential of landscape approaches and its practice, and funding and policy implications.

The dialogue aimed to inform on-going practices of participants, and feed into policy dialogues organised as part of the TCforBE project and within the Global Landscapes Forum. The results aim to provide evidence of how landscape approaches fit into transformative change as framed by IPBES and the upcoming [Scoping report for a second global assessment of biodiversity and ecosystem services](#).

Fifty participants (see Appendix 1 List of participants) joined in person and online. These come from research, government, finance, conservation and development organisations, NGOs, business and consultancies who are involved in developing, implementing, financing and evaluating landscape approaches for livelihoods and conservation aims. As the majority of participants are based in the Netherlands and are members or in the network of the CCLI, the scope of experiences shared was Dutch based and so indirectly reports on Dutch based NGOs partnerships with global south actors. The CLLI intends to facilitate exchange coordinated through Dutch NGOs by connected to local partners and their experiences.

The program was organised to first present evidence (see links in Table 2) and then to exchange on four questions:

1. What's working (or not) and via which change pathways – with what impacts and outcomes, and for who? (Addressing questions of power, framing, hegemony, inclusiveness, legitimacy, equity, trade-offs, spillage and synergies)
2. How transformative are landscape approaches?
3. What understandings and lessons can we distil from our experiences and research?
4. Where are knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps?

Participants shared details of publications and outputs that can help answer these questions. These are shown in Appendix 2 Data and evidence shared.

We are disseminating the results of the dialogue with:

1. The Dutch based [Collaborative Landscape Learning Initiative \(CCLI\)](#). The CCLI provides a platform, safe space and an organized process to facilitate inter vision among peers from different backgrounds and organisations in The Netherlands. It allows peers to keep each other updated on operational issues on the one hand and connects practitioner and policy makers experiences with the scientific knowledge base on landscape approaches. It aims to strengthen an informed and inclusive dialogue between the practitioner organizations and policy makers, representing a diversity of voices from the landscapes themselves, which advances strategic programming and effective and coherent policy development. Insights gained are documented and communicated as policy relevant lessons which meet strategic knowledge needs of policy makers and practitioners in The Netherlands.
2. The [Landscape Practitioner Network](#) of 20 international certification standards, conservation and development organizations convened by ISEAL Alliance.
3. Through the [TC4BE](#) and [CCLI](#) websites, on [Zenodo](#) with the TC4BE#, and on social media (Linked In [TC4BE](#) and our personal pages).

Table 2 Landscape dialogue program 19 March 2025

Time	Activity	Aims	Who	Online activity
09.00	Introductions	Introduce meeting aims Participant introductions Introducing Transformative change Introducing GLF	Verina Ingram, Wageningen UR Cora van Oosten, GLF CIFOR-ICRAF	Online
09.30-12.00	15-minute presentations and 15-minute Q&A	Critical reflections on landscape approaches and principles, and evidence of effectiveness	James Reed, CIFOR-ICRAF	Online questions & reflections via MIRO
Break		Typology for diversity in landscape approaches – Preliminary findings	Katie Minderhoud, PBL	
		IDH landscape programs environmental & social impacts - approaches and experiences from practice	Violaine Berger & Leony Aurora, IDH	
		Aligning on the core criteria for mature landscape initiatives'	Billie Wilcox Brooke, ISEAL Alliance	
		Bridging Knowledge Gaps in Landscape Restoration: Commonland's Evidence Gap Map Approach	Milena Engel, Commonland	
12.00-12.45	Lunch			
13.00 – 13.30	20 minutes in-depth talking walk	<i>What understandings and lessons do you distil from the experiences, research and lessons shared?</i>	All participants	Online participants Share via Miro
13.30 - 14.30	World café format Breakout group discussions + shared insights	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>What's working (or not) and via which change pathways?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What understandings and lessons do we distil from our experiences and research? - What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps? <i>What impacts and outcomes, and for who?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What understandings and lessons do we distil from our experiences and research? - What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps? <i>How transformative are landscape approaches?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What understandings and lessons can be distilled from experiences and research? - What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps? 	Self-reporting groups with 'table managers	Breakout groups Miro
15.15		Synthesis of responses to 3 questions	Wenny Ho	Feedback online
15.45	Closing plenary	Wrap up Next steps Upcoming events CCLI Upcoming events GLF	Verina Ingram & Thirze Hermans Katie Minderhoud & André Brassier Kimberly Merten	Online
16.00 - 16.30	Drinks & nibbles in the sun		All participants	

3. Dialogue results

This chapter synthesizes the dialogues, structured using the four questions.

3.1 What understandings and lessons can be distilled from the experiences, research and lessons shared?

1. **Landscape approaches are defined and understood differently³** (We first need to define what it they are (boundaries) before we can answer whether it works and have impact or not. There is conceptual ambiguity, which presents a risk that the concept is coopted, and a lack of basic norms results in poor design. [ISEAL's criteria for claim making](#) help provide some common language for cooperation.
2. **Evidence is lacking.** Despite some ten to fifteen years of using the approach, there is little empirical evidence that it works.
3. **Principles and values could be made explicit as common understandings/definition in LA.** As Integrated landscape approaches inherently have power issues, there is a need to capture absent voices, of communities, of private sector. Especially with externally driven landscape approaches is it necessary to have a political dimension included and power issues addressed explicitly. How to build connecting from what is already there? (Wageningen UR) summarising the discussions.
4. **Many toolkits exist³** which support designing and implementing LAs.
5. **ILAs benefit from being connected to national and international policy processes**
6. **Inclusive and adaptive governance** is required for transformative LAs.
7. **Scale is important** as there are limits to the physical area a multi stakeholder platform can govern.
8. Dealing with **illegality and informality** is important – but often contradicts with perceptions of government stakeholders who may prefer to exclude stakeholders acting in this way.
9. **Governance** could synergistically overcome multiple barriers to landscape transformation, i.e., responds to conflicting objectives, poor stakeholder coordination, and instances of corruption.
10. **Processes that make explicit how data is generated and shared** are required for inclusive governing and buy in.
11. **LAs are not the only approaches** to bring together multiple stakeholders, there are other 'consensus' approaches which maybe more suited in contexts of intense struggles and highly political processes.
12. **Monitoring, learning and evaluation are critical to evidencing success of LAs**, but often under budgeted and need to be built into long term financing. Building in questions around causation, attribution and contribution is important, as well as clarifying learning purposes and audiences.
13. To better engage with the realities of complex tropical landscapes, integrated landscape approaches need to be **long-term and transdisciplinary**.
14. Moving away from often **false dichotomies**, and adopting a systems approach that prioritizes process and adaptation to determine enabling conditions and lessons learned, will likely be more constructive to the long-term sustainability of integrated landscape approaches.
15. Research that attempts to **measure the things that count as well as counting what can be measured** is fundamental to building the evidence base and helping understand under what conditions ILAs are workable and who benefits.
16. Site-level focus alone cannot deliver justice or sustainability. Landscape approaches with a focus on conservation need to **expand their focus and extend collaborations across sectors and extend to different spatial scales and relevant policy levels to address underlying drivers and realise transformative change**.

³ See presentation [Critical reflections on landscape approaches and principles, and evidence of effectiveness](#) by James Reed.

3.2 What's working (or not) and via which change pathways?

Lessons

- Borders are challenging as they are multi-dimensional (embracing power, area, actors, values, time policy and governance), which requires in depth understanding of dynamics both inside and outside landscape.
- Replicating or connecting to existing, local governance and market structures can help changes happen, but need to be careful they do not reinforce the status quo. A challenge is therefor to maintain positive changes when structures stay the same. Often this seems to work better with small changes than radical ones.

Whats working:

1. Use leading (future oriented) indicators instead of performance (past-oriented) indicators
2. Using entry points via "common" concerns to provide a convening focus.
3. Building and connecting new and old (governance and management) structures.
4. Understanding what "mature" LAs are is needed to allow stakeholders to recognise when different phases are reached and different processes, criteria and configuration are needed, including in governance and monitoring, evaluation and learning⁴
5. Using existing projects and programmes and partners to lever outcomes.
6. Building a business case for a landscape approach, rather than (shorter term) project or programs⁷
7. When we take into account and understand the **historical context**
8. Create adaptive capacities for resilience
9. Change decision making and enabling conditions as prerequisite of success
10. Unrestricted funding is available for experimentation/innovation
11. Connect actors across scales and build agency to take balanced decisions
12. Have indicators on how data/information flows and changes over time
13. Understand the sum of parts and what are the signals we need to pay attention to at global, national, regional and local scales

Whats not working:

1. The roles of government in governance at a landscape scale are sometimes limited by their technologies. Can change? - Can address by system analysis + good stakeholder roles
2. Establishing common concerns and entry points often resonate more with select groups of stakeholders, but need to resonate with local people
3. "Unusual suspects"⁸ also need to be invited to the stakeholder table
4. How stakeholders are determined in ILA (often results in elite capture + powerful interests)
5. Sharing failings and South-South learning so we learn from failure and don't repeat it.
6. Using jargon. To measure impact, we need clearer, practical and consistent language which does not allow different interpretations of criteria.
7. Asking our partners the right questions to get the right information.
8. Most internal documents were not originally designed for impact reporting, but incorporating this element in the future could be valuable.
9. Learning and impact monitoring – this should be part of everything we do.
10. We need to expect that there will be unintended and unexpected impacts + consequences
11. Power is often forgotten – but landscapes are per definition political economy spaces.
12. The conceptual ambiguity and term landscape approach is too open to interpretation
13. Evidence presented to date is largely positive - that most initiatives seem to be working, but this seems unrealistic and implausible.
14. Many "KPIs" used for measuring are top down, arguably we need to be measuring processes and power.
15. The location of many landscape approaches shows a focus on biodiversity (i.e. prioritising the environment and biodiversity over poverty alleviation, which is more widespread) whilst ignoring the elephant in room rather than poverty landscapes.
16. Understanding differences between governance and management
17. Need for unrestricted funding to develop creative interventions. Funding is therefore essential, for a long(er) periods.

⁴ See Billie Wilcox Brooke's presentation [Aligning on the core criteria for mature landscape initiatives'](#)

What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps?

- Understand the scaling of Landscape approaches.
- Consistency in understanding effectiveness, what are possible interventions that enhance effectiveness? How to operationalize 'effectiveness'?
- How is landscape resilience created, and when is it reached?
- Understanding unintended and unexpected impacts of interventions in landscape approach
- Data- there is significant potential to enhance our data. Many partners report extensively, but do not report on where the gaps still are.
- technical skills in house, like data analysts and researchers who can easily gather data, with careful attention for transparency and accessibility of data and analysis of data for all actors.
- Theories that help understand and explain short term and long term effects of interventions and when to do what,
- Relations between incremental and transformational change?⁵ Incremental improvements can be part of a transformational change, but how to support what by whom is not clear.
- Competences and capacity to understand changes i.e. language about changing values and assets / ownership, dealing with conflicts of interests

Photo 1 Dialogue facilitated by James Reed (CIFOR-ICRAF)

3.3 What impacts and outcomes, and for who?

What understandings and lessons do we distil from our experiences and research?

- To enable nuanced understanding of the diversity in intent, approach and implementation, landscape approaches could be classified into **typologies**⁶, to make dimensions of governance that are often implicit and invisible, more explicit. This would help better grasp changes in governance structures and capacities by operationalizing and investigating governance elements, comparing and contrasting between typology profiles what works where and why, and exploring the extent the landscape approach can/does deliver on transformative change and the enabling factors

⁵ There is a body of knowledge on transformational-incremental change and on dis/continuous change.

⁶ See Katie Minderhoud's presentation [Typology for diversity in landscape approaches – Preliminary findings](#)

- Assessing impacts by using **layers⁷ and different scales** can give insights to assess effectiveness and changes in governance.
- Impacts for different groups of people in general, given the multi stakeholder context, and often prior activities in a landscape, make it very difficult to claim (and prove) **attribution and impacts – but easier to claim contribution**.
- Making the distinction between **top-down or locally owned** is difficult, most approaches seem top down but become (or aimed to become) bottom up and owned.
- Incorporating **local values** was noted as challenging, but essential given the importance of cultural values.
- Measuring impacts for **voiceless “ghosts”** could be measured as when voiceless stakeholders do/can speak out in front of others.
- Making **trade-offs between impacts** visible and transparent in design and evaluation. Low confidence in evidence from internal documents and higher confidence in scientific, systematic, external reviews with can tells us about interactions/trade-offs of impact areas, set up a long-term research agenda and provide a baseline of evidence to helps understand where we want to go⁸.
- There is a lot of **scientific evidence** that participatory monitoring positively affects different impact areas/ returns, that supporting communities has a positive effect, and restoration measures aimed solely on restoration, have a positive impact on natural returns, but there is less evidence that they have social, financial and inspirational impacts. short-term (1-3 years) project funding can have negative effects on restoration projects, but there is no evidence that long-term funding has a positive effect on different social, ecological, inspirational and financial impacts⁸.
- Impacts appear associated with how **decision-making is facilitated** over time, with observations that it changes as the role of facilitator/convenor/financers change
- Many experiences indicated that **timescales for monitoring, evaluation and measuring** often did not capture impacts early on (i.e. around first five years), particularly ecological impacts such as visible signs of restoration.
- **Strong alliances** appear to be a supporting and enabling factor – but come with the perceived disadvantage of being top down, highlighting how difficult it is to have local engagement whilst creating and stimulating transformative change in a landscape.
- **Multi stakeholder approaches** might not work or be needed in all phases of a LA, and different approaches (i.e. consensus, directive, bottom up) could be more effective to create impacts at different time (example given by Wetlands international in India.
- **Budget and financing** affect the flows of impacts and is generally underestimated, particularly the time and budget to start and maintain multi stakeholder processes.

What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps?

- Robust evidence, mapping gaps as well as impacts and effectiveness, including cost effectiveness and positive and negative economic and social costs and returns
- Evidence gaps on social, natural, financial, and inspirational returns or impacts and certain types of interventions, little evidence on the effects of regenerative businesses on natural, social and financial returns⁹
- Gaps in convening/facilitating/leading capacities, including critical reflection on the roles taken at different stages in a landscape process and convenor’s positionality.
- Dealing with absent voices “ghosts” - including the technologies available to better include and hear them
- How to enhance adaptive capacity
- Baseline studies
- Incorporation of other knowledges (with a dominance of Western, scientific knowledge in most approaches), particularly local knowledge

⁷ See Violaine Berger’s presentation [IDH landscape programs environmental & social impacts - approaches and experiences from practice](#)

⁸ See Milena Engel’s presentation [Bridging Knowledge Gaps in Landscape Restoration: Commonland’s Evidence Gap Map Approach](#)

Photo 2 Participants in one of the dialogues facilitated by Katie Minderhoud (PBL)

3.4 How transformative are landscape approaches?

- Asking whether **landscape approaches are transformative** or not is not the right question. The question should be “what causes change?” “Are we at the right nodes?” and are LAs supporting adaptive and resilient livelihoods and environments?
- It was questioned if **transformative change is even necessary**? And that incremental change could also be OK. Also recognizing the scale of transformation could be from individual to company to a system and is not on a fixed time scale.
- Transformative change can be **highly temporal**: it could happen fast, and may not necessarily take a long time, but can also be very short term, and can reverse (partly). So, ideas of change should not be seen as linear and unidirectional. A question is if LA are not working or just, they are not yet transformative?
- As transformative change occurs on individual and system levels, the processes of change, i.e. through **new/changed relations and connections** is also important.
- LAs are not “value free”, so recognizing and attention to changes in **values** underpinning changes in systems, and associated changes in power, on (in)equity and justice), is important. Narratives are one way to monitor changes in values.
- Could LAs be seen as transformative even if a **majority of stakeholders values/practices/beliefs do not change**? or if not, all agree with the changes or where power imbalances stay the same? Or when stakeholders stop engaging who previously have engaged?
- Transformation should be **determined by the people who live and experience it**
- Change was seen to be associated with the **financer(s), facilitators and conveners** - who “allow” power to be changed, mediating between and recognizing different values.
- It was questioned if people are **equipped (have capacities) to be transformative, and that resilience** should be a focus, equipping people and environment to deal with shocks
- Landscape approaches work better when: embedded in a larger enabling environment (so that enabling conditions as prerequisite of success), create adaptive capacities for resilience and are transformative in changing decision-making, and connect actors across scales and build agency to take balanced decisions and include horizontal and vertical coherence
- **Scenarios and modeling** can help to project possible futures for a landscape, and see over time how transformation unfolds
- Governance **levers for change** (see presentation 6 on leverage points) could be process changes/levers.
- Creating **measures of transformation** was not common – for example IDH⁷ doesn't aim to be or monitor transformative change but uses key performance indicators (KPIs) determined by coalition partners.
- Concrete activities, “strategic acceptance” and collaboration (actors speaking with each other) were seen as critical starting points for transformative change

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- are we at the right nodes → social tipping points for strategic acceptance
- Change can occur when stakeholders are at the table who want, can and will effectuate change and is within their sphere of influence (for example, national government change directly affects the landscape context but may be out of our sphere of influence)

Pathways to change?

- Via markets, water, resource and land use rights (as objects of change)
- bringing together already identified/financed priorities and building on them
- investing in existing projects - scaling
- New (or adopted) governance structures, policies – especially new landscape level management/governance boards
- Training and capacity building
- Asking inhabitants and stakeholders what is needed and targeting specific actors with needs
- innovation / knowledge sharing
- investing money to do the right thing - different premises
- consensus based Theory of change
- value group cups get sidelined
- including government stakeholders
- need explainer -> why shared LA -> what is the readiness of situation & intent
- Locally embedded entry points
- Covering high costs of multi stakeholder processes with reliable, consistent and long term funding (when there is no guarantee of tangible (upfront agreed) outcomes) is a major challenge in bringing stakeholders together
- look for resistance movements and what is seen as threatening and addressing these

What are the knowledge, research, competence and capacity gaps?

- How governance structures are integrated in local policy
- Timelines that can be expected to see returns
- On which stakeholders to focus who need support to make change
- Consistent definitions of LA outcomes
- Creative ways of supporting stakeholders to define impacts and outcome

Photo 3 Dialogue facilitated by Katie Minderhoud (PBL) and Wenny Ho (Wageningen UR)

6. Conclusions

The main conclusions of the dialogue with academic, implementing and financing stakeholders of landscape approaches about their impacts and potential to bring about transformative change at landscape scale, for different and multiple social, economic and environmental goals in the context of sustainable development, are that:

- There is a tendency to think in **dichotomies**: e.g. localization or trans local relations, projects or processes. The distinction between a top-down versus locally led approach can be a false dichotomy. Instead a key issue is how to align and to synergize interventions. Yet, who to involve and who owns an initiative is ambiguous: who are the partners, and who is not included explicitly or unintentionally?
- Often not all **stakeholders** – those with an interest, influence, impact, cost of benefit - are included because they are not seen by (some) other stakeholders as legitimate or as illegal, but exclusion can mean a problem is not solved.
- There is no common agreement on what **learning in landscape approaches** can result in: learning should not happen in a vacuum but contribute to desired/envisioned changes. Learning does not seem to figure as a (support) pathway for transformative change.
- **Power** is talked about, but from the discussions clear stands, positions, and values seem to be implicit in most approaches, Equally, the mechanisms by which power is channelled - governance and management arrangements (statutory, policies, specific new landscape level platforms, and customary norms and tradition) are not always a focus of attention. However for transformation change that has positive impacts for multiple impacts or returns for multiple stakeholders, and makes explicit and deals with potential trade-offs, managing power inequities and justice is critical, This is especially in commodity landscapes with histories of injustices.
- **Lessons learnt** include the need for improved conceptualization and a definition of landscape approach - as a transdisciplinary, long-term, systems approaches that prioritizes process and adaptation - are needed. These can build on existing toolkits to better incorporate social values and perceptions, capture absent voices and include boundary spanning partners. The consistent presence of a local champion or convenor/facilitator who is reflective of their own interest and positionality appears critical, as is data accessibility and regular, meaningful stakeholder engagement. Actions across scales, transdisciplinary, and multi-sectoral that target drivers of social-environmental aims and contribute to building resilience and adaptive capacity can help.
- There are **limitations to landscape approaches** and given the long term intervention needed, costs, scale and need for appropriate convening/facilitation they may not be an effective pathway for transformational change in different agrifood landscapes.
- Stakeholders designing and implementing need to consider whether to **start from zero** (often with externally driven and funded initiatives) versus understanding and building on existing institutions, considering history etc. A landscape is a multi-dimensional concept, an island in time and space, but that is layered, embedded and connected at different scales which are important to consider for effective change.
- There is an ongoing discussion about **monitoring, measuring and types of indicators**, that clashes with notions of emergent change and design. Monitoring for (external) financiers may require very different evaluation tools from monitoring and learning for/by/with stakeholders within the landscapes,
- Considering the **long-time frames** for LAs to be effective and that most funding is for much shorter timescales than needed before an approach matures and is self-sustaining – implementing LAs seems to require moving away from seeing change processes as linear and transformation to being seen as both short-term and long-term. This implies unpacking what change means and looks like from different perspectives and analysing how (multi-level, multi actor) change happens.
- Academic and traditional, local **knowledge, increased capacities and research** is needed to fill gaps, connect dots, and evaluate progress.

Photo 4 Wenny Ho summarising the dialogue (Wageningen UR)

Appendix 1 List of participants

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D6.2 Landscape Approaches Dialogue

Appendix 2 Data and evidence shared

The presentations can be accessed online:

Introducing Transformative change Introducing GLF	Verina Ingram, Wageningen UR Cora van Oosten, GLF CIFOR- ICRAF
Critical reflections on landscape approaches and principles, and evidence of effectiveness	James Reed, CIFOR-ICRAF
Typology for diversity in landscape approaches – Preliminary findings	Katie Minderhoud, PBL
IDH landscape programs environmental & social impacts - approaches and experiences from practice	Violaine Berger & Leony Aurora, IDH
Aligning on the core criteria for mature landscape initiatives'	Billie Wilcox Brooke, ISEAL Alliance
Bridging Knowledge Gaps in Landscape Restoration: Commonland's Evidence Gap Map Approach	Milena Engel, Commonland

